

Gender Discrimination in Childhood Education at Chitwan District

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Abstract

Exploring gender discrimination in academic literature remains a subject of ongoing global discourse. Despite endeavours to offer free primary education in Nepal, gender inequality in education persists as a formidable obstacle, particularly concerning the access and academic success of young girls. Numerous socioeconomic hurdles that households encounter delay girls' educational participation and accomplishments. This study examined the factors that influence gender discrimination in girls' access to quality education. Employing a mixed-methods approach, this study's data collection incorporated both quantitative and qualitative methodologies to foreground the research phenomenon. Data was gathered through questionnaires and semi-structured interviews and subsequently analyzed using descriptive statistics and content analysis. The research encompassed 251 female high school students from grades 9 to 12, selected using purposive and simple random sampling methods.

The quantitative findings reveal a significant correlation between parental preference for enrolling girls in preschool, the gender gap in girls' academic performance, the influence of sibling care on girls' academic success, and parental economic status on girls' educational attainment. Similarly, the results revealed a correlation between the limited availability of school resources and girls' education, parental religious beliefs affecting girls' schooling, and socio-cultural factors influencing children's school enrollment and girls' access to quality education. The ramifications of gender discrimination in childhood education within the Chitwan District hold considerable significance, as they provide insights into the obstacles girls encounter in accessing education. By addressing these challenges, the research contributes to broader social development objectives and empowers girls to realize their potential as active participants in society.

Keywords: *allocation of resources, childhood education, educational performance, girls' educational rights, gender disparity, household resources, socioeconomic*